

GEODESIC GRAPHOIDAL COVERING NUMBER OF THE CORONA PRODUCT OF PATHS AND CYCLES

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ABSTRACT. If each path of ψ is a shortest path in G , then a graphoidal cover ψ of a graph G is said to be a geodesic graphoidal cover of G . It is denoted by $\psi_g(G)$. The least cardinality of a geodesic graphoidal cover, $\psi_g(G)$, is referred to as the geodesic graphoidal covering number of a graph G . It is represented by $\eta_g(G)$. Within this study, we establish geodesic graphoidal covering number for the corona product of paths and cycles.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

All the graphs used in this study are finite, undirected, and contain no multiple edges or loops. Some standard notions and symbols used in this article are as follows. We represent the set of all the vertices for the given graph G by $V(G)$ and the set of edges by $E(G)$. The cardinality of the set of vertices (order of the graph G) is represented by p , and the cardinality of the set of edges (size of the graph G) is represented by q . If $P = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m)$ represents a path or a cycle within a graph G , then the vertices u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{m-1} are known as the internal vertices of P , and u_1 and u_m are referred to as the external vertices of P . If there is no vertex in G that serves as an internal vertex of both P_1 and P_2 , then two paths, P_1 and P_2 , are considered internally disjoint. For more terminologies in graphs, refer to [10].

The study of graphoidal cover was first proposed by Acharya and Sampathkumar [1] and subsequently explored in greater depth in [2–4, 6, 12]. The study of the geodesic graphoidal covering number of a graph was introduced by Arumugam and Suresh Suseela [11] and it was further studied by G. Thiyagarajan [5]. The study of graphoidal cover for the corona product was studied by P. Titus and S. Santha Kumari [9] and further investigated in [7, 8].

Definition 1.1. [1] A graphoidal cover of a graph G is a collection ψ of paths within G , which may not necessarily be open, satisfying:

- (i) Each path in ψ contains a minimum of two vertices.
- (ii) Each vertex in graph G is an internal vertex in at most one path from ψ .
- (iii) Each edge of graph G belongs exclusively to one path in ψ .

Definition 1.2. [1] The graphoidal covering number of graph G is defined as the least cardinality of a graphoidal cover of graph G . It is represented by $\eta(G)$.

Definition 1.3. [11] If each path of ψ is the shortest path in G , then a graphoidal cover ψ of a graph G is said to be a geodesic graphoidal cover of G . It is represented by $\psi_g(G)$.

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The least cardinality of a geodesic graphoidal cover, $\psi_g(G)$, is referred to as the geodesic graphoidal covering number of a graph G . It is represented by $\eta_g(G)$.

Product graphs are utilized to create mathematical representations of complex networks that reflect the characteristics of real-world networks. Corona graphs, in particular, are constructed by applying the corona product to fundamental graphs.

Definition 1.4. [7] The corona product of two graphs Q and R , denoted as QoR , forms the corona graph of those two graphs.

QoR is formed by one copy of Q and p (order of graph Q) copies of R , where the j^{th} vertex of Q is connected to all vertices in the j^{th} copy of R .

In this study, we aim to further investigate the geodesic graphoidal covering number by focusing on the involvement of paths and cycles. Our objective is to determine the geodesic graphoidal covering number for corona graphs of path and cycle.

2. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1. *If $G = P_m o P_n (m, n \geq 2)$, then $n_g(G) = m(n + 1) - 1$.*

Proof. Let us suppose $P_m = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m$, and $P_n = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n$ are paths of length m and n , respectively, where $m, n \geq 2$. Let the graph G is the corona product of P_m and P_n , i.e., $G = P_m o P_n$. Graph $G (P_m o P_n)$ is depicted in Figure 1.

let $Q_1 = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, v_{m1}$; $Q_{i+1} = v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{in-1}, v_{in}$, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m-1, m$; $S_1 = \bigcup_{j=2}^n (u_1, v_{1j})$; $S_2 = \bigcup_{i=2}^{m-1} \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij})$ and $S_3 = \bigcup_{j=1}^{n-1} (u_m, v_{mj})$. Clearly every $Q_i (1 \leq i \leq m+1)$ and every $S_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ is a geodesic path.

Therefore, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_m, Q_{m+1}, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$ is a minimum geodesic graphoidal cover of G . Hence, $n_g(G) = m + 1 + n - 1 + n(m - 2) + n - 1 = m(n + 1) - 1$. So, $n_g(G) = m(n + 1) - 1$.

□

Corollary 2.2. *If $G = P_n o P_m (m, n \geq 2)$, then $n_g(G) = n(m + 1) - 1$.*

Corollary 2.3. *If $2 \leq m \leq n$, then $n_g(P_m o P_n) \leq n_g(P_n o P_m)$.*

Proof. It is given that $m \leq n$, this implies that $mn + m - 1 \leq mn + n - 1$, i.e., $m(n + 1) - 1 \leq n(m + 1) - 1$. Hence, $n_g(P_m o P_n) \leq n_g(P_n o P_m)$. □

Theorem 2.4. *If $G = C_m o P_n$, then $n_g(G) = m(n + 1)$, where $m \geq 3$ and $n \geq 2$.*

Proof. Consider $C_m = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, u_1 (m \geq 3)$ as a cycle of order m and $P_n = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n (n \geq 2)$ as a path of length n . Given that the graph G is a corona product of cycle C_m and path P_n , i.e., $G = C_m o P_n$. Graph G is depicted in Figure 2.

Case I: If m is even.

FIGURE 1. Graph $G = P_m o P_n (m, n \geq 2)$.

Let $Q_1 = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{m}{2}}, u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+11}$;

$Q_2 = u_1, u_m, u_{m-1}, \dots, u_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+21}$;

$Q_3 = u_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}$;

$R = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, where $R_i = v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i(n-1)}, v_{in}$ be a path of length n ;

$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij})$

Clearly, every $Q_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ and each element in R and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+11}), (u_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+21})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + m + mn - 3 = m(n + 1)$.

Case II: If m is odd.

Let $Q_1 = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{m-1}{2}}, u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}$;

$Q_2 = u_1, u_m, u_{m-1}, \dots, u_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}+11}$;

$Q_3 = u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, u_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}$;

$R = \bigcup_{i=1}^m R_i$, where $R_i = v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i(n-1)}, v_{in}$ be a path of length n ;

$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij})$

Clearly, every $Q_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ and each element in R and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}), (u_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}+11})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + m + mn - 3 = m(n + 1)$.

As a result, $n_g(G) = m(n + 1)$, where $m \geq 3$ and $n \geq 2$. □

Theorem 2.5. $G = P_m o C_n$ implies that, for any $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 3$, $n_g(G) = m(n + 3) - 1$.

Proof. Let $P_m = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{m-1}, v_m (m \geq 2)$ is a path of length m , and let $C_n = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1}, u_n, u_1 (n \geq 3)$ is a cycle of order n . Consider the graph G is the corona product of the path P_m and the cycle C_n , i.e., $G = P_m o C_n$. Graph $G (P_m o C_n)$ is depicted in Figure 3.

Case I: If n is even.

Let $Q = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, v_{m1}$;

$R_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1})$;

FIGURE 2. Graph $G = C_m o P_n (m \geq 3, n \geq 2)$.

$$R_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in-1}, v_{in});$$

$$R_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{in}, v_{i1});$$

$$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij}).$$

Clearly, Q and every element of R_1, R_2, R_3 and S is a geodesic path. Thus, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q, R_1, R_2, R_3, S - (u_1, v_{11}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . Hence, $n_g(G) = 1 + 3m + mn - 2 = m(n + 3) - 1$.

Case II: If n is odd.

$$\text{Let } Q = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, v_{m1};$$

$$R_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1});$$

$$R_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in}, v_{i1});$$

$$R_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1});$$

$$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij}).$$

Clearly, Q and every element of R_1, R_2, R_3 and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q, R_1, R_2, R_3, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}\}$ is a minimum geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 1 + 3m + mn - 2 = m(n + 3) - 1$. Therefore, $n_g(G) = m(n + 3) - 1$. □

Theorem 2.6. *If $G = C_m o C_n$, then $n_g(G) = m(n + 3)$, for any $m, n \geq 3$.*

Proof. Let $C_m = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, u_1 (m \geq 3)$ and $C_n = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1}, u_n, u_1 (n \geq 3)$ are cycles of order m and n , respectively. Let the graph G is a corona product of two cycles C_m and C_n , i.e., $G = C_m o C_n$. Graph G is depicted in the Figure 4.

Case I_1 : If m and n are both even.

FIGURE 3. Graph $G = P_m o C_n (m \geq 2, n \geq 3)$.

Let $Q_1 = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{m}{2}}, u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+11}$;
 $Q_2 = u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, u_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, v_{m1}$;
 $Q_3 = u_m, u_1$;
 $R_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1})$;
 $R_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in})$;
 $R_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{in})$;
 $S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij})$.

Clearly, every Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , and every element of R_1, R_2, R_3 , and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R_1, R_2, R_3, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+1}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + 3m + mn - 3 = m(n + 3)$.

Case I_{II} : If m even and n is odd.

It is observed that Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , and S remain the same in case I_{II} as in case I_I .

Let $R'_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1})$;
 $R'_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in-1}, v_{in}, v_{i1})$;
 $R'_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1})$;

Clearly, every Q_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) and each element of R'_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R'_1, R'_2, R'_3, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+1}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + 3m + mn - 3 = m(n + 3)$.

Case II_I : If m is odd and n is even. Let $Q_1 = v_{11}, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{m-1}{2}}, u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}1}$;

$Q_2 = u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, u_{\frac{m+1}{2}+1}, \dots, u_{m-1}, u_m, v_{m1}$;
 $Q_3 = u_m, u_1$;
 $R_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1})$;
 $R_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in})$;
 $R_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{in})$;
 $S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcup_{j=1}^n (u_i, v_{ij})$.

Clearly, every Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , and every element of R_1, R_2, R_3 , and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R_1, R_2, R_3, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}1}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + 3m + mn - 3 = m(n + 3)$.

Case II_{II} : If m and n are both odd.

FIGURE 4. Graph $G = C_m o C_n (m, n \geq 3)$.

It is observed that Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , and S remain the same in case II_{II} as in case II_I .

$$\text{Let } R'_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{i\frac{n-1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}});$$

$$R'_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+2}, \dots, v_{in-1}, v_{in}, v_{i1});$$

$$R'_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^m (v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{i\frac{n+1}{2}+1});$$

Clearly, every Q_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) and each element of R'_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) and S is a geodesic path. Hence, $\psi_g(G) = \{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, R'_1, R'_2, R'_3, S - \{(u_1, v_{11}), (u_{\frac{m+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{m+1}{2}}), (u_m, v_{m1})\}\}$ is a least cardinality geodesic graphoidal cover of G . So, $n_g(G) = 3 + 3m + mn - 3 = m(n + 3)$. Therefore, $n_g(G) = m(n + 3)$ for all $m, n \geq 3$. □

3. CONCLUSION

This study presents the geodesic graphoidal covering number for corona products of paths and cycles. We conclude that $n_g(P_m \circ P_n) = m(n+1) - 1$, $n_g(C_m \circ P_n) = m(n+1)$, $n_g(P_m \circ C_n) = m(n+3) - 1$, and $n_g(C_m \circ C_n) = m(n+3)$. In the future, the geodesic graphoidal covering number of the corona product for various graphs can be studied.

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